

Real-Time Sign Language Interpretation System

Avantika Mishra, Soumya P. Panda*, Isha Bharadwaj, Annada Gumansingh, Anmol Ray

Department of CSE, Silicon University, Odisha, India

Abstract- This work focuses on designing a real time sign language interpretation system that may recognize different signs in real time and interpret the information in text form to the users. Dynamic hand gesture recognition is performed by applying image classification techniques. The model takes sign language images from the webcam as input, process them and convert them into respective written textual formats. For this purpose, TensorFlow Object Detection API is used and transfer learning mechanism is applied using SSD MobileNet. The presented model is tested on varied samples presented by different persons and the results obtained in all the experiments performed shows the effectiveness of the presented model in correctly interpreting the sign language words from image to respective text format with an average accuracy of 95%.

Keywords—Sign language interpreter, Movement recognition, Object detection, Transfer learning, Sign Language Recognition

I. INTRODUCTION

Communication is very crucial to human beings, as it enables to express or convey the feelings to others [1]. There are different modes of communications used by human to interact with each other such as: speech, gestures, body language, reading, and writing or through visual aids [2]. However, integrating the deaf and mute community into the conversational world is a challenging task. For the people with speaking or hearing disabilities, there are numerous challenges arises in day today life to communicate with the common people creating a communication gap between those minority groups with the common people. People with speaking or hearing disabilities often uses visual aids or an interpreter for communication [3]. However, those methods are rather cumbersome and expensive, and may not be feasible in emergency situations [4]. Therefore, sign language-based communication mode is being adopted by majority of such people. In this regard, the common people find it difficult to understand the different signs or gestures used to communicate different aspects. Also, recognizing the diverse range of sign languages present around the globe and providing feasible platforms to interact with the deaf and mute community is still a challenging task [5][6].

Sign languages include different hand gestures, movements of hands, face, and body as the main form of communication mediums conveying some specific meanings [7][8]. Those languages are not very common for the common people to understand. Sign Language Recognition (SLR) systems are crucial in eliminating this communication gap between the common people and the people with speech disabilities. Those systems may recognize different gestures and translates them into corresponding written text in a language [9][10]. Different SLR models have being presented by researchers, however, the accuracy of such models is always a major concern due to the size of the available dataset and clarity of images considered [11][12]. A real-time sign language interpreter in this aspect can detect and interpret sign language gestures to text format in real time [13][14][15].

This work focuses on designing a real time sign language interpretation system that may recognize different signs in real time and interpret the information in text form to the users. Dynamic hand gesture recognition is performed by applying image classification techniques. The

model takes sign language images from the webcam as input, process them and convert them into respective written textual formats. For this purpose, TensorFlow Object Detection API is used and transfer learning mechanism is applied using SSD MobileNet. The presented model is tested on varied samples presented by different persons and the results obtained in all the experiments performed shows the effectiveness of the presented model in correctly interpreting the sign language words from image to respective text format with an average accuracy of 95%.

II. RELATED WORK

Several models have been put forward since decades for automatic classification of sign languages [1]. [10] discusses about classification of different leap motion sensor and using the K-Nearest Neighbor and Support Vector machine. However, the models achieve an average accuracy of 72.78% and 79.83% respectively. [15] presented a Deep Convolutional Neural Networks based SLR system that focuses on complex head and hand movements along with their changing shapes. The researchers in [9] discusses about a deep convolutional network that focuses on large-scale image recognition and applied RNNs to capture the long-term temporal dependencies. To extract spatial features, VGG16 is pretrained on ImageNet and the extracted features are fed to a stacked GRU. [6] discusses about a 3D convolutional network to establish the representation of frames and the relationship between frames. Recognizing sign language gestures from continuous videos is still a major challenge in continuous videos [11]. Due to recent advancement in classification methods, many of the recent proposed works contribute on the classification methods, such as hybrid method and Deep Learning [12]. However, availability of training data set, clarity of the images used and the time of getting the results are still major challenges in designing real time sign language detection systems and is the focus of the work presented in this paper.

III. PROPOSED MODEL

To implement this model, different images were collected from varied internet sources and are labeled with their respective text version labels. Images were also collected by the help of OpenCV to leverage webcam to collect images for training. LabelImg, an open-source package is used to label images for object detection. The model is trained on different commonly used sign language words. A total of 1500 images were considered for preparing the data set covering 100 commonly used words in day today conversations such as: “Hello”, “Yes”, “No”, “Sorry”, “Please”, “Thank You, etc. The overview of the presented sign language interpretation system is presented in Figure. 1. The presented model recognizes the sign language using TensorFlow Object Detection API by performing transfer learning using Single Shot Detector (SSD) MobileNet [13]. It recognizes different hand gestures by capturing photos in real time using a webcam. We aim at performing dynamic hand gesture recognition by applying video classification. We wish to develop a system that may take in sign language as input from the webcam, convert it into text and display the relevant translation as output.

Fig.1 Overview of the Real-Time Sign Language Interpretation System

The use of SSD makes the model more dynamic and faster by taking one single shot to detect multiple objects within the same image. Use of small convolutional filters in SSD helps in improving the accuracy. The SSD object detection model consists of 2 components: feature map extractor, and convolution filters to detect objects. To enable continuous improvement, two approaches are used. First by changing hyperparameter values during training we obtained the optimal results. We tried training with 5000, 10000, 15000 and 20000 training steps, and found that the optimal results are obtained for 10000 training steps. Secondly, by changing the dataset slightly and re-labelled the changed images the overfitting issues are avoided. We re-trained the changed dataset and found that the model predicts better without overfitting.

IV.RESULTS

The presented model performs transfer learning against the TensorFlow API for object detection to detect the sign language gestures in real time. It detects different commonly used significant American sign language gestures. The model is implemented in python environment model and use the webcam from Google Colab to capture real-time data. It captures images and processes the frame to identify different poses and map them to respective text formats. Several experiments were performed to evaluate the performance of the proposed model. For this purpose, the speakers of 3 categories were considered: female, male and child. Experiments were performed by capturing the videos of sign gestures with different backgrounds such as: office, home, day time, evening time, late night. Figure. 2. Shows the example outputs of real-time sign language detection performed at home environment from webcam for a female speaker for some common words. Figure. 3 shows the average accuracy percentage of some selected example words for the considered speakers and environments.

Fig. 2 Example outputs of real-time sign language detection performed at home environment from webcam

The SSD MobileNet based model for sign language classification is also compared with other two classifiers: K-nearest neighbor and SVM trained on similar environment. For this purpose, three categories of speakers were considered: male, female, and child. The average accuracy percentages obtained in all the experiments for the models are listed in Table.1 and a comparison is presented in Figure. 4. The proposed model achieves approximately 95% accuracy with an increase of more than 15% over the traditional classifiers showing the effectiveness of the presented model in real time sign language detection. Also, the model is evaluated with respect to the precision and recall measures. The presented model achieves an average precision score of 95.2% and recall score of 94.6% in the experiments performed.

Fig. 3 Average accuracy % of some example words by the proposed model

TABLE.1. ACCURACY OF DIFFERENT MODELS

Models	Accuracy %		
	Female	Male	Child
K-nearest neighbor	71.68	72.78	72.76
SVM	78.81	79.83	79.82
Proposed Model	94.6	95.4	95

Fig.4 Accuracy % of the models

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a TensorFlow object detection API is considered for real time detection of different sign languages. The system is trained on the different sign gestures for some commonly used English terms. For data acquisition, images were captured by a webcam using Python and OpenCV which makes the cost cheaper. The presented model is tested on several sign languages by different speakers and achieves a high average confidence rate in all the experiments performed. The presented model achieves approximately 95% accuracy with an increase of 15% over the traditional classifiers. However, this work may further be enhanced by increasing the number of words in the training gesture so that the system can recognize more gestures and may be made more dynamic.

REFERENCES

- [1] Daiyi Peng, Xuanyi Dong, Esteban Real, Mingxing Tan, Yifeng Lu Hanxiao Liu, Gabriel Bender, Adam Kraft, Chen Liang, Quoc V. Le, "PyGlove: Symbolic programming for automated machine learning", *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, Vol. 33, pp. 96-108, 2020.
- [2] Zhang Shujun and Qun Zhang, "Sign language recognition based on global-local attention", *Journal of Visual Communication and Image Representation*, Vol. 80, Article id: 103280, 2021.
- [3] I. A. Adeyanju, O. O. Bello, and M. A. Adegboye, "Machine learning methods for sign language recognition: A critical review and analysis", *Intelligent Systems with Applications*, Vol. 12, Article id: 200056, 2021.
- [4] Brandon Garcia, Sigberto Alarcon Viesca, "Real-time American Sign Language Recognition with Convolutional Neural Networks", Stanford University Stanford, CA, 2016
- [5] Sawant Pramada, Deshpande Saylee, Nale Pranita, Nerkar Samiksha, Mrs.Archana S. Vaidya, "Intelligent Sign Language Recognition Using Image Processing", *IOSR Journal of Engineering (IOSRJEN)*, Volume 3, Issue 2, PP 45-51, 2013
- [6] Pratibha Pandey, Vinay Jain, "An Efficient Algorithm for Sign Language Recognition", *(IJCSIT) International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technologies*, Vol. 6, 2015
- [7] K. S. Sindhu, Mehnaaz, B. Nikitha, P. L. Varma and C. Uddagiri, "Sign Language Recognition and Translation Systems for Enhanced Communication for the Hearing Impaired," 2024 1st International Conference on Cognitive, Green and Ubiquitous Computing (IC-CGU), Bhubaneswar, India, 2024, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/IC-CGU58078.2024.10530832
- [8] Ashish .S. Nikam and A. G. Ambekar, "Sign language recognition using image based hand gesture recognition techniques," 2016 Online International Conference on Green Engineering and Technologies (IC-GET), Coimbatore, India, 2016, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/GET.2016.7916786.
- [9] J. Carreira and A. Zisserman, "Quo Vadis, Action Recognition? A New Model and the Kinetics Dataset," 2017 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR), Honolulu, HI, USA, 2017, pp. 4724-4733, doi: 10.1109/CVPR.2017.502.
- [10] C. H. Chuan, E. Regina and C. Guardino, "American Sign Language Recognition Using Leap Motion Sensor," 2014 13th International Conference on Machine Learning and Applications, Detroit, MI, USA, 2014, pp. 541-544, doi: 10.1109/ICMLA.2014.110.
- [11] M. Soundarya, M. Yazhini, N. Thirumala Sree, N. Sornamalaya and C. Vinitha, "Sign Language Recognition Using Machine Learning," 2024 International Conference on Advances in Computing, Communication and Applied Informatics (ACCAI), Chennai, India, 2024, pp. 1-7, doi: 10.1109/ACCAI61061.2024.10602025.
- [12] X. Xu and J. Fu, "A two-stage sign language recognition method focusing on the semantic features of label text," 2024 20th CSI International Symposium on Artificial Intelligence and Signal Processing (AISP), Babol, Iran, Islamic Republic of, 2024, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/AISP61396.2024.10475205.
- [13] D. Niranjan, B. VinayKarthik and Mohana, "Performance Analysis of SSD and Faster RCNN Multi-class Object Detection Model for Autonomous Driving Vehicle Research Using CARLA Simulator," 2021 Fourth International Conference on Electrical, Computer and Communication Technologies (ICECCT), Erode, India, 2021, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/ICECCT52121.2021.9616712.
- [14] C. Gao, Y. Zhai and X. Guo, "Visual Object Detection and Tracking System Design based on MobileNet-SSD," 2021 7th International Conference on Computer and Communications (ICCC), Chengdu, China, 2021, pp. 589-593, doi: 10.1109/ICCC54389.2021.9674450.
- [15] Y. Yamashige and M. Aono, "FPSSD7: Real-time Object Detection using 7 Layers of Convolution based on SSD," 2019 International Conference of Advanced Informatics: Concepts, Theory and Applications (ICAICTA), Yogyakarta, Indonesia, 2019, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/ICAICTA.2019.8904089.